

Stakeholders' Perceptions on Maritime Spatial Planning

« This kind of initiative is valuable
to better understand each other »

Maritime Spatial Planning Directive (2014/89/EU)

Objectives

Reduce
conflicts
between sectors

Environmental
Quality
Targeted by MSFD

Cross-Border
Cooperation

Encourage
Investments
By creating predictability

« At sea, there
is now a diversity
of activities.
It becomes a sort
of need to
organise things. »

Some guiding principles ...

Holistic Approach
To address every maritime sectors' needs

Ecosystem-Based
Approach

Stakeholder
engagement

Coherence between
Sector-Based Policies

Land-Sea
interactions
To be taken into account

How it is among our neighbours?

MSP in France ...

MSP in Spain ...

MSP in Portugal ...

OSPAR IV region at stake

MARINE ENVIRONMENT

Marine Protected Areas

349 MPAs
(200 N2000 MPAs)

18.1% of OSPAR IV
Region covered
by MPAs

18 different MPA
categories over
the three countries

Coastal areas better
covered (33.2%) than
offshore waters (15.6%)

- Deep-sea ecosystems
- Seagrass beds
- Seabirds
- Small dolphins
- Fin whale
- MPA

ECONOMIC SECTORS

The region is:

37%
of the EU aquaculture
production

527M€
of turnover
for fishing

More than 1600
swimming areas and
500 marinas

- Aquaculture
- Operational windfarm
- Windfarm in project
- Oil and gas exploitation
- Main port

Stakeholders' opinion

INTERVIEWS

ROUND TABLES

POST-IT SESSIONS

BOARD GAMES

What they say
about...

MSP Process

EXPECTATIONS OF COMMON REFERENCES

LACK OF COORDINATION AT EVERY LEVEL

EXPECTATIONS OF STREAMLINED LICENSING PROCEDURES

What they say about...

Stakeholder engagement and governance

EXPECTATIONS OF AN EARLY ENGAGEMENT

NEED FOR CROSS- BORDER COOPERATION

EXPECTATIONS OF MORE CONSULTATIONS WITH LESS MEETINGS

"We haven't been consulted enough on the planning process."

"1000 pages to read! Of course we didn't read it... We don't have time for it!"

What they say
about...

Environment and
conservation

CONSENSUS ON THE NEED FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

"We need sustainable development!"

... OUR INTERESTS
ARE NOT TAKEN
INTO ACCOUNT

“For planning, we
focus on economic
activities, but not
on environmental
protection.”

“As usual,
environmental
objectives
are more
important.”

WHO IS RESPONSIBLE?

What they say about... Blue Economy

EXPECTATIONS OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT AND VISIBILITY

EXPECTATIONS OF CONFLICT RESOLUTION

CONCERNS ABOUT RESTRICTIONS AND DISCRIMINATORY TREATMENTS

To be continued...

THE EXPECTATION THAT MSP...

...harmonizes transnational policies and fosters cross-border cooperation;

...brings greater coherence between policies and the implementation of directives at national level ;

...encourages knowledge sharing and collecting.

NOVA

"Hey look,
they're
getting
their act
together!"

"Thank
goodness! I
think we're
going to make
it..."

thank you!
merci!
gracias!
obrigado!

